

Learning to Improve Gender Equality: An Analysis of Software Engineering Education in a UK University

Supplementary Figures and Questionnaire for GE@ICSE 2024 Submission

Section 1: Graphical visualizations of the raw data provided in Table 2 of the paper.

Figure A: Yearly Comparison of Average Program Scores in Undergraduate Computer Science and Software Engineering by Gender

Figure B: Yearly Comparison of Average Graduation Scores in MSc in Software Development by Gender: Full-Time and Part-Time Students

Figure C: Yearly Comparison of Average Graduation Scores in MSc in Software Development by Gender: Full-Time Students Only

Figure D: Yearly Comparison of Average Graduation Scores in MSc in Software Development by Gender: Part-Time Students Only

Section 2: Questions used in the student questionnaire.

Q: What is your age?

This closed-ended question provides a set of age ranges, from '18-29 years old' to 'Over 70 years old,' allowing individuals to select the category that represents their age group.

Q: What is your gender?

This closed-ended question asks respondents to indicate their gender, offering the options 'Female,' 'Male,' and 'Non-binary'.

Q: What is your mode of study?

This closed-ended question invites respondents to specify their mode of study by selecting either 'Full-time' or 'Part-time'.

Q: Have you had any experience in programming or software engineering before starting this course? (If yes, describe your experience. If no, explain why not.)

This question begins with a binary choice ('yes' or 'no') and allows collection of more detailed information through open-ended questions.

Q: How confident do you feel about your current programming or software engineering knowledge?

A closed-ended question with a Likert scale ranging from 'Extremely confident' to 'Not at all confident,' which assesses self-perceived proficiency in programming or software engineering.

Q: How confident are you in your ability to succeed in this course?

A closed-ended question with a Likert scale ranging from 'Extremely confident' to 'Not at all confident,' which assesses self-perceived proficiency in programming or software engineering.